

DERMATOLOGICAL AND PHYTO THERAPEUTIC POTENTIALS OF AYURVEDIC HERBS: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Background: The growing preference for natural and safe cosmetic product has increased global interest in *Ayurvedic* cosmetics which use herbal ingredients supported by traditional knowledge and scientific evidence. **Aim:** This review aims to analyze the *Ayurvedic* herbs with dermatological and cosmetic relevance, and their application in cosmeceutical formulations. **Methods:** *Ayurvedic* literature as well as modern electronic database were reviewed. Studies focusing on formulation strategies, phytochemistry and dermatological actions of *Ayurvedic* herbs were reviewed. **Result:** *Ayurvedic* texts describe the herbs for their complexion enhancement, anti-aging, anti-inflammatory and skin protective effect. Key phytoconstituents were studied exhibiting photoprotective and antioxidant action. Incorporation of modern delivery systems such as exosomes, nanoemulsions and hydrogels improves the stability. Quality control measures ensure safety and efficacy of formulation. **Conclusion:** *Ayurvedic* herbs possess significant potential as effective and safe alternatives to synthetic cosmetic ingredients. Integration of traditional knowledge with modern formulation technologies support the development of scientifically valid herbal cosmeceuticals for dermatological application.

KEYWORDS: *Ayurvedic* cosmetics, Herbal cosmeceuticals, phytoconstituents, nanoemulsions, exosomes, hydrogels.

INTRODUCTION

Cosmetics is defined as any article that is applied to any part of human body for cleansing, beautifying, to promote attractiveness or alter one's appearance.^[1]

According to World Health Organization (WHO), about three-quarters of the world population depends on traditional medicines (mainly herbs) for their healthcare. Ayurveda and Chinese medicinal systems are the most acceptable traditional system which has a considerable amount of research on pharmacognosy, chemistry, pharmacology and clinical therapeutics.^{[2][3]}

Ayurvedic cosmetics also known as herbal cosmetics focus on using the essential oils, herbs and plant extracts

and are formulated to support skin vitality and offer relief from various dermatological concerns.

Ayurvedic cosmeceutical product which include lipsticks, shampoos, toothpaste, body and hair oil, soaps, sun blocking cream or gel, moisturizer, facial scrub etc. have gained much recognition and became very popular among the consumers. These products have anti-oxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-bacterial and anti-acne properties.

Ayurvedic cosmetic approach go beyond the topical application of various herbal cosmetic products incorporating the detoxifying therapies like *Panchkarma* and *Rasayana* which are essential to maintain external

appearance and skin health in ayurveda.

METHODS

A literature search was conducted utilizing the Ayurvedic texts, Google Scholar, PubMed, and ScienceDirect databases. Studies focusing on the dermatological properties, active phytoconstituents and formulation strategies were reviewed.

Various herbs mentioned in ayurvedic text having dermatological and cosmetic properties

Varnya Gana: Candana, Punnaga, Padmaka, Usira, Madhuka, Manjistha, Sariva, Payasya, Sitalata these ten are complexion promoting drugs.^[4]

Vayasthapan Gana: Amruta (Guduchi), Haritaki, Amalaka, Yukta, Sweta, Jivanti, Atrisa, Mandukaparni,

Sthira and Punarnava these ten are age sustainer.^[5]

Kusthaghna Gana: Khadira, Haritaki, Amalaka, Haridra, Ballatak, Saptapana, Aragvadha, Karavira, Vidanga, tender leaves of Jati these ten are anti-dermatosis.^[6]

Kandughna Gana: Candana, Nalada, Aragvadha, Naktamala, Nimba, Kutaja Sarsapa, Madhuka, Daruharidra and Musta these ten are anti pruritic.^[7]

Eladi Gana: Ela, Tagara, Kushta, Mansi Dhyamaka, Tvak Patra, Nagapushpa, Priyangu, Harenuka, Vyaghranakha, Valuka, Sukti, Canda, Sthauneyaka, Srivestaka, Coca, Coraka, Aguru, Sprikka, Usira, Bhadradaru, Kumkuma, Punnaga, and Kesara (nagakesara) this Eladi Gana mitigates Vata, Kapha and poison, bestows goods colour cure itching eruptions and rashes.^[8]

Dermatological Uses and Applications of Phytoconstituents of Various Herbs

S.No.	Herbs	Active constituents	Dermatological use	Applications	References
1.	Sandalwood (<i>Santalum album</i>)	Alpha-and beta-santalol	Anti-Inflammatory, Skin Whitening Property	Facepack, Sunscreen	[9] [10]
2.	Aloe vera (<i>Aloe barbadensis miller</i>)	Barbaloin, aloesin,	Anti Pigmentation Anti-Inflammatory	Gel, Facewash, Toner	[11] [12]
3.	Manjistha (<i>Rubia cordifolia</i>)	Rubiadin	Anti-Inflammatory, Antioxidant	Facepack	[13]
4.	Bakuchi (<i>Psoralea corylifolia</i>)	Bakuchiol	Anti-Aging, Anti-Pigmentation, and Anti-Acne	Serum, Moisturiser	[14]
5.	Neem (<i>Azadirachta indica</i>)	Nimbin Azadirachtin	Antioxidant And Antibacterial	Facewash, Toner	[15]
6.	Amla (<i>Embllica officinalis</i>)	Quercetin, Gallic acid	Antioxidant, Skin whitening property	Cream, Facewash	[16] [17]
7.	Gojihva (<i>Borago officinalis</i>)	Gamma-linoleic acid	Anti-Aging, Anti Inflammatory	Gel, Moisturiser,	[18]
8.	Khas (<i>Vetiveria zizanioides</i>)	Vetiver oil	Anti Acne Antiaging	Moisturizer, Toner,	[19]
9.	Daruharidra (<i>Berberis aristata</i>)	Berberine, Epiberberine	Anti-Inflammatory, Antioxidant,	Gel	[20]
10.	Haldi (<i>Curcuma longa</i>)	Curcumin, Curcuminoids	Antioxidant, skin whitening property	Sunscreen, Facewash	[21]
11.	Yahtimadhu (<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i>)	Gabridin, Glycyrrhizin	Antioxidant And Inhibit UVB	Sunscreen, Facepack	[22] [23]
12.	Nirgundi (<i>Vitex negundo</i>)	Negundin A	Anti Pigmentation	Sunscreen	[24] [25]
13.	Khadir (<i>Acacia catechu</i>)	Catechin, Catechutannic acid	Antioxidant, Skin Whitening	Cream	[26]
14.	Kusumbh (<i>Carthamus tinctorius</i>)	Margaric acid	Anti-Melanogenic Activity	Sunscreen	[27] [28]
15.	Sariva (<i>Hemidesmus indicus</i>)	Hemidesminine, Lupeal, vanillin	Antioxidant, Tyrosinase inhibotry activity	Toner, cream	[29] [30]

Dermatological Benefits of Ayurvedic herbs

1. Anti-inflammatory Effect

Anti-inflammatory are the agents possessing the cox 1 and 2 inhibition.^[31] Ingredients like turmeric (*Curcuma longa*),^[32] adrak (*Zingiber officinale*),^[33] sandalwood

(*Santalum album*),^[9] possess natural anti-inflammatory properties that may help reduce redness, swelling, and acne.

2. Antioxidant Activity

Antioxidant are the substance that protects cells and

tissues from the oxidative damage caused by free radicals. Some exogenous antioxidants are vitamin E, vitamin C, and lipoic acids. Many Ayurvedic herbs are rich in antioxidants (e.g., *Mustaka*(*Cyperus rotundus*),^[34] khadir(*Acacia catechu*),^[35] amla(*Emblca officinalis*),^[36] which help fight oxidative stress and premature skin aging.

3. Moisturization and Skin Barrier Repair

The skin barrier relies on the stratum corneum for protection against exogenous substances and moisturizing factors. This layer of the skin has acidic pH which plays a vital role in maintaining skin barrier functions.^{[37][38]} Natural oils like papaya (*Carica papaya*)^[39] sandalwood oil (*Santalum album*),^[40] and cucumber (*Cucumis sativus*)^[41] are often used to nourish and hydrate the skin, improving elasticity and barrier function.

4. Skin Whitening and depigmentation

Anti-tyrosinase activity of some herbs inhibits the production of melanin which reduces skin hyperpigmentation and leads to skin whitening. Hydroquinone [HQ], arbutin, kojic acid are some chemical agents used for skin whitening and depigmentation. Herbs like saffron,^[42] padma^[43] and khadir^[44] are traditionally used for hyperpigmentation, dark spots, and enhancing skin radiance.

5. UV Protection

Prolonged exposure to UVA and UVB radiation can cause various types of skin damage, including sunburn, skin ulcers, photoaging, and even skin cancer. The active constituents of traditional medicines have proven efficacy in treating UV induced skin damage demonstrating antioxidant and DNA repair properties.^[45] Some herbs demonstrating mild UV protection effect are shankhpushpi,^[46] kalmegh^[47] and walnut.^[48]

6. Anti acne activity

Acne occurs when pores on skin become clogged by bacteria, debris or infection. Some medicinal plants extracts used to treat acne are onion,^[49] Shalmali^[50] Ashwagandha.^[51]

Modern Formulation Strategies Using Ayurvedic Herbs

Therapeutic Strategies

Exosomes, hydrogels, and nanoemulsions these three strategies have been used for improving the delivery of active components and skin repair. These systems address critical challenges associated with conventional treatments, such as limited bioavailability, stability, and targeted delivery, by leveraging unique properties like nanoscale size, biocompatibility, and controlled release mechanisms.

Exosomes - Exosomes excel in protecting and transporting bioactive molecules while facilitating cell communication and regeneration. Some naturally derived

exosomes are wheat,^[52] ginger,^[53] garlic.^[54]

Hydrogels - Hydrogels provide transdermal drug delivery, effective in wound healing and prevention of infection, high moisture retention, and improved stability for plant extracts. Plant extract in hydrogel are curcumin,^[55] neem,^[56] jatamansi.^[57]

Nanoemulsions - Nanoemulsions are nano-sized emulsions, which are manufactured for enhancing the delivery of active pharmaceutical ingredients.^[58] Some herbal sources of cosmetic nanoemulsions are Curcuma aromatica,^[59] ingudi (terminalia catappa)^[60] and bakuchi (*Psoralea corylifolia*).^[61]

Integration of Natural Actives in Cosmetic Formulations

Many of the natural products such as arbutin (melanin inhibiting), azulene (antioxidant and anti-inflammatory), carnolic acid (antioxidant), glycyrrhizin (skin whitening), rutin (antioxidant), squalene (emollient), rosmarinic acid (antioxidant) are used in various cosmetic preparations. These active ingredients are formulated to increase skin elasticity, delay in skin aging by reducing the wrinkles, protection against UV radiation by antioxidant property and to check degradation of collagen respectively.

Quality Control Standards for Medicinal Plants

The increasing demand of herbal extract in cosmetic products is increasing, and with this increase in demand it is the primary requirement to maintain the quality of drug. To address this issue, herbal materials or products pass through various chemical tests and techniques, such as HPLC, Gas Chromatography, UV-Visible Spectroscopy, Heavy metal contamination. This allows Ayurvedic actives to compete with synthetic ingredients in terms of efficacy, shelf life, and formulation stability.

DISCUSSION

In ayurveda beauty is not only external beauty but the healthy state of both mind and body which is reflected not only through a clear and vibrant face but also as a graceful and attractive presence throughout the entire body. The term cosmetology is given by modern science but before that acharyas had already described the cosmetic properties of various herbs and divided them accordingly. Ayurveda has described various gana and varga which consist various herbs having cosmetic and dermatological properties. Ayurvedic texts describe numerous herbs within the context of *Dinacharya* that are not only essential for maintaining internal health but also contribute to cosmetic enhancement, including skin clarity and hair health.

The increasing demand of cosmetics has made many irresponsible people using harmful elements on their face leading to allergy, sensitivity, dark spots and many other skin conditions. So, some specific herbs which are safer to use having cosmetic value are enlisted with their

properties.

CONCLUSION

In this review we discussed about various ayurvedic herbs and their phytochemicals demonstrating their dermatological uses and their application in modern cosmetic products. These herbs are being used widely for their anti hyperpigmentary, anti - acne, anti - aging and skin brightening constituents in herbal cosmetic industries. Many plant extracts contain some active constituents which are comparable or act as substitute for synthetic chemical constituent. It explores the formulation strategies, including exosomes, hydrogels, and nanoemulsions, which enhance the delivery, stability, and bioavailability of these natural actives. The emphasis on quality control standards, ensures that Ayurvedic drug actives can effectively compete with synthetic constituents in terms of efficacy and shelf life.

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